

A new inchworm piezoelectric rotary motor with optimized vibration and frictional slipping effects

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ABSTRACT

Inchworm rotary motion with high-precision and large-stroke properties is increasingly required in micro/nano alignment applications. However, the precision of current piezoelectric inchworm motors is severely deteriorated by poor step consistency under different frequencies because of undesired contact vibration and frictional slipping. In this article, an inchworm piezoelectric rotary motor with high step consistency is developed. A new compliant soft contact and rotary mechanism (CSCRM) is designed and optimized to achieve soft and stable contact, and then rotate the output platform in sequence, passively suppressing vibration with two-level compliant contact stiffness. Importantly, to analyze the triggering condition of frictional slipping, a contact-friction model is presented to build the relationship between the driving signals (including acceleration) and the friction. Then, the boundary conditions of frictional slipping are deduced from the contact-friction model and used to optimize driving signals in value, sequence and shape. FEA simulation verifies the optimized results of mechanical parameters. In addition, a prototype is fabricated and tested with comparative experiments. The experimental results uniformly confirm that the developed piezoelectric rotary motor can achieve microradian resolution with 3.3 μrad , speed of 42.81 mrad/s , and load-bearing capacity of 2 kg in a highly linear and stable manner. More importantly, the contact vibration and frictional slipping are nearly eliminated, leading to almost no rollback and highest step consistency among current literature, i.e., 93% within 100 Hz. It is also worth noting that the designed motor can continuously work across different frequencies without readjusting the initial gap.

1. Introduction

In the post-Moore era, chip shows the trend of miniaturization and high integration, which puts forward stringent requirements for high-precision chip alignment operation [1–3]. For example, in the process of MicroLED mass laser transfer, large-stroke and high-precision rotary alignment (accuracy $< \pm 5 \mu\text{rad}$, stroke $> 3^\circ$) between chip carrier and display substrate is greatly required for correcting the angle deviation [4–6]. Additionally, achieving high-stroke and high-precision angle deviation adjustment of chip bumps on 12-inch wafer is essential for wafer-scale direct packaging [7, 8]. Therefore, the rotary stage with large stroke and microradian accuracy has become a key challenging for developing an advanced chip packaging techniques [9, 10].

To solve this challenge, researchers mainly proposed two methods: macro-micro composite stage and inchworm piezoelectric motor [11–13]. The former generally uses a linear motor to generate large-stroke macro motion, and the micro motion is realized by a compliant mechanism driven by piezoelectric actuator in a small range [14, 15]. However, the alignment efficiency and precision in this composite mode are limited by switching strategy of macro-micro motion and dynamic processing of feedback signals [16, 17]. On the other hand, the inchworm piezoelectric motor simulates the step-by-step movement of the inchworm organism to achieve large stroke and high precision (see Fig. 1(a)). Different from the stick-slip motion [18, 19], the inchworm motor can directly control the displacement with independent motion of contact-actuation-separation, obtaining larger stroke and higher precision [20]. For example, Liu et al. [21, 22] designed a piezoelectric actuator based on simplified inchworm rotary motion to achieve efficient rotary motion with desirable properties. Manhong Li et al. [23] developed a soft pipe robot based on the soft limbs and efficient motion mode of inchworm, which can coordinately control each actuator to motion orderly with the cooperation of control system by reasonably optimizing modular actuators based on deformation analysis.

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Fig. 1. Step inconsistency of the current piezoelectric inchworm motors. (a) principles and working flow of inchworm motion, (b) step inconsistency caused by overlarge rigid contact vibration, (c) step inconsistency caused by frictional slipping.

However, the precision of current inchworm motors are severely deteriorated by step inconsistency [24], caused by nonlinear vibration and frictional slipping:

- (1) High-frequency repeated rigid contact will generate large impact, which leads to overlarge nonlinear vibration and hence seriously affects the step consistency (see Fig. 1(b)).
- (2) The frictional slipping will happen when the dynamic actuation force exceed frictional force, as the actuation force containing acceleration will increase with frequency and meanwhile the contact force would not (see Fig. 1(c)).

Currently, a few pioneering studies have been carried out to improve the continuity of inchworm motion from adjustment of initial contact gaps [25, 26]. Yang et al. [27] designed a piezo-driven positioning platform with alterable initial gap between contact surfaces to test the influence of initial gap on backward motion under specific frequency. Moreover, Wang et al. [28] also presented a stick-slip piezoelectric actuator to investigate the effects of initial gap on the one-stepping characteristics with changeable initial gap. However, the current research only analyze the influence of initial gap on frictional slipping with discrete tests and control the initial contact force. In fact, the frictional slipping is related to dynamic actuation force (including acceleration) and contact force rather than only the initial contact force [29, 30]. In these pioneering studies, the initial gap must be readjusted when the actuation frequency is changed, as the acceleration will change with frequency. Therefore, it is necessary to suppress the contact vibration and analyze the influence of dynamic actuated force and contact force on frictional slipping under different frequencies.

To address these key issues, a new inchworm piezoelectric rotary motor with high step consistency is developed. Specifically, a compliant soft contact and rotary mechanism (CSCRM) with two-level contact stiffness and direct rotary output properties is designed and optimized, which can reduce contact vibration and realize stable rotation. Moreover, to overcome frictional slipping, a contact-friction model is presented to build the relationship between frictional force and driving signals of rotary actuation and contact, obtaining non-slipping boundary condition with limited acceleration. Then, a smooth dual-driving strategy and driving signals of rotary actuation and contact are optimized based on the non-slipping boundary condition to gain non-slipping rotation under different frequencies without readjusting initial gap. Finally, a prototype experiment system is tested and gained highest step consistency among current piezoelectric motors, proving the effectiveness in reducing vibration and frictional slipping effects.

The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows. 1) An inchworm piezoelectric rotary motor based on CSCRM is developed, which can effectively reduce rigid contact vibration and enhance contact stability through

Fig. 2. The mechanical design of CSCRM. (a) CSCRM with contact module and rotary module, (b) vibration absorption principle by two-level compliant parallelogram mechanisms in contact module, (c) comparison of contact characteristics.

mechanical design. 2) A smooth dual-driving strategy based on developed contact-friction model is proposed, avoiding frictional slipping under different frequencies without readjusting initial gap and gaining highest step consistency in the literature. The rest of this article is organized as follows. The mechanical design of the rotary motor is demonstrated in Section 2. The dynamic models are established in Section 3. Then, the parameters and actuated signals are optimized in Section 4. In Section 5, the validation experiments and performance evaluations are performed. Finally, conclusions are summarized in Section 6.

2. The design of flexure-based rotary motor based on inchworm motion

This section presents the mechanical design of the CSCRM and the rotary motor based on inchworm motion. Subsequently, the working principle and working flow of the designed piezoelectric rotary motor are analyzed.

2.1. The design of CSCRM

In order to obtain high-precision and large-stroke rotary motion, the inchworm motion principle is adopted, which can periodically superpose small step to obtain large stroke with high precision [31, 32]. However, high-frequency periodical contact-separation process will inevitably cause an impact on output platform, resulting in nonlinear contact vibration.

Hence, to improve dynamic stability of the contact process in inchworm motion, a compliant soft-contact and rotary mechanism integrated with contact module and rotary module is designed, which can achieve contact and rotary motion independently, as shown in Fig. 2(a). On the one hand, the two sets of compliant parallelogram mechanisms provide two-level contact motion stiffness and damping effect for the CSCRM driven by PZT-1, which plays a buffering role and produces soft contact to reduce vibration. Compared to rigid contact, the designed CSCRM can absorb the contact vibration through passive elastic deformation and damping of flexure hinge, as shown in Fig. 2(b). Moreover, when the contact occurs between two surfaces, the deformation of the soft-contact head can be utilized to indicate the contact force in real time.

On the other hand, the rotational motion is driven by PZT-2 installed along the direction of 45° , which is conducive to a compact and lightweight structure. Under the actuation of PZT-2, the soft-contact head of CSCRM will generate rotational motion through the bending deformation of the circular flexible hinge at the bottom. Importantly, with this tilted arrangement and tilted actuation mode, the driving force generated at the contact point between the CSCRM and rotor platform has a vertical component that can enhance the contact status, which improves stability compared to horizontal actuation, as shown in Fig. 2(c).

To further improve the speed and stability of rotation, two CSCRMs are symmetrically mounted around the output platform to form a decoupled dual-driving motion, as shown in Fig. 3. A high-precision cross-roller bearing is used as the rotary center, and the wear-resistant alumina ceramics on the output platform are used to improve the stability and working life. The position adjustment slides can quickly adjust the initial gap between CSCRMs and output platform before work. Finally, the proposed inchworm piezoelectric rotary motor is obtained.

Fig. 3. The proposed piezoelectric inchworm rotary motor.

2.2. Working flow of the designed rotary motor

In general, to ensure the accuracy and reduce rollback of piezoelectric rotary motor, it is necessary to maintain positional consistency and stability at transferring points when switched to the next step, as shown in Fig. 4(a) and (e). Therefore, the sequence of dual-driving signals of CSCRM is crucial, and the working flow of the designed piezoelectric rotary motor is analyzed as follows:

- (1) Installation and calibration: install each CSCRM stably and adjust the initial gap (only one time for all different frequencies) between soft-contact head and alumina ceramic block (see Fig. 4(b)).
- (2) Contact and rotation of CSCRM-1: from time t_0 to t_2 , actuating PZT-1 to make the CSCRM-1 stably contact with alumina ceramic block, and then actuating PZT-2 to make CSCRM-1 rotate output platform simultaneously (see Fig. 4(c)~(d)).
- (3) Contact of CSCRM-2 and reset of CSCRM-1: from t_2 to t_3 , actuating PZT-3 to make the CSCRM-2 contact with alumina ceramic block and hold the position. And reset PZT-1 and PZT-2 to their initial positions from t_3 to t_4 .
- (4) Rotation of CSCRM-2: from t_3 to t_5 , actuating PZT-4 to make CSCRM-2 rotate the output platform. Then, actuating PZT-1 to hold the position of the output platform. From t_0 to t_5 , the movement of the dual-driving rotary motor within one cycle is completed (see Fig. 4(f)).

By repeating the working sequence above, a large-stroke and high-precision rotary motion could be obtained. Compared with the traditional inchworm rotary motor, the proposed CSCRM has the following advantages: 1) CSCRM adopts a soft-contact module and rotary module to generate contact and rotation motion in sequence, and can enhance contact stability through the vertical component force of rotary module. 2) two groups of compliant parallelogram mechanisms with two-level contact stiffness can effectively reduce contact vibration, and the deformation of the soft-contact head can be used to indicate contact force and then ensure a better contact status. Besides, the designed dual-driving working flow ensures continuity of the rotary motion without rollback. It should also be noted that the reverse rotation can be achieved when the working sequence of the PZTs in CSCRM is changed, and the adopted driving method can theoretically achieve full-stroke rotation.

3. Modeling of the designed piezoelectric inchworm rotary motor

As mentioned above, the rotation is actually dynamic process with acceleration, which could generate overlarge actuated force and hence result in frictional slipping. Thus, it is necessary to build the contact model to analyze the

Fig. 4. The working flow of the proposed inchworm piezoelectric rotary motor. (a) superposition principle of large-stroke rotary motion, (b) initial status, (c) contact motion actuated by PZT-1, (d) rotary motion actuated by PZT-2, (e) comparison of different driving methods, (f) dual-driving signals of PZTs.

contact force (directly related to friction force) and hence the analytical compliance model of the CSCRM is established. Moreover, the boundary conditions of frictional driving is critical to eliminate slipping and hence the contact-friction model is established.

3.1. Compliance modeling of CSCRM

Based on the knowledge of mechanics, the compliance matrix method is commonly used to establish the compliance of compliant mechanisms [33, 34]. Considering that the designed CSCRM is symmetric in stiffness, the overall output compliance can be calculated through left branch. The compliance of a single flexible hinge in the plane can be expressed as follows:

$$C = \frac{X}{F} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta x/F_x & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \Delta y/F_y & \Delta y/M_z \\ 0 & \Delta \theta/F_y & \Delta \theta/M_z \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where F_x , F_y , and M_z are the components of the force along the X -axis, Y -axis and the torque around the Z -axis of the flexible hinge at the output point, respectively.

Then, the output compliance of the whole compliant mechanism can be obtained by transformation of the coordinate system and relationship of series or parallel of a single flexible hinge, and the schematic structure of CSCRM is shown in Fig. 5. The input point O_{in2} of PZT is compliant parallelogram mechanisms grouped by four straight beam flexible hinge. So, the compliance in O_{R2} of compliant parallelogram mechanism can be calculated as follows:

$$C_{O_{L5}}^{O_{R2}} = T_{O_{L5}}^{O_{R2}} C_{O_{L5}} (T_{O_{L5}}^{O_{R2}})^T \quad (2)$$

Fig. 5. Structural parameters of the CSCRM.

$$T_{O_{L5}}^{O_{R2}} = P_{O_{L5}}^{O_{R2}} R_{O_{L5}}^{O_{R2}} \quad (3)$$

$$P_{O_{L5}}^{O_{R2}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \left(p_{O_{L5}}^{O_{R2}} \right)_y \\ 0 & 1 & -\left(p_{O_{L5}}^{O_{R2}} \right)_x \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$R_{O_{L5}}^{O_{R2}} = R(\pi/2) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\pi/2) & -\sin(\pi/2) & 0 \\ \sin(\pi/2) & \cos(\pi/2) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$C_{O_L}^{O_{R2}} = \left[(C_{O_{L5}}^{O_{R2}})^{-1} + (C_{O_{L6}}^{O_{R2}})^{-1} + (C_{O_{L7}}^{O_{R2}})^{-1} + (C_{O_{L8}}^{O_{R2}})^{-1} \right]^{-1} \quad (6)$$

where R_i^j and P_i^j are rotary matrix around Z-axis and translation matrix along X-axis or Y-axis from coordinate O_i to O_j , respectively.

Furthermore, the CSCRM also includes circular flexible hinges C_{OR} for connection and rotation, which connects with compliant parallelogram mechanism in series. And the compliance in point O_{R2} can be expressed as follows:

$$C_{O_{R2}} = C_{O_L}^{O_{R2}} + C_{OR2} \quad (7)$$

Finally, according to the symmetry relationship in stiffness, the output compliance $C_{rotary-out}$ and $C_{contact-out}$ of CSCRM at the output point O_{out} can be obtained similarly:

$$C_{rotary-out} = \left[(T_{OR2}^{O_{out}} C_{OR2} T_{OR2}^{O_{out}T})^{-1} + (T_{OR1}^{O_{out}} C_{OR1} T_{OR1}^{O_{out}T})^{-1} + (T_{OR3}^{O_{out}} C_{OR3} T_{OR3}^{O_{out}T})^{-1} \right]^{-1} \quad (8)$$

$$C_{OL}^{Oout} = \left[(C_{OL1}^{Oout})^{-1} + (C_{OL2}^{Oout})^{-1} + (C_{OL3}^{Oout})^{-1} + (C_{OL4}^{Oout})^{-1} \right]^{-1} \quad (9)$$

$$C_{\text{contact-out}} = C_{OL}^{Oout} + C_{Ocon}^{Oout} \quad (10)$$

where C_{Ocon}^{Oout} represents the compliance of soft-contact head after contact with the surface of alumina ceramic.

3.2. Contact-friction modeling of the rotary motor

In order to eliminate the frictional slipping in the dynamic process of the inchworm rotary motor, the relationship between the contact force and the friction force should be clarified. Therefore, the analysis of contact status such as contact force F_{con} and frictional status is needed to ensure the step consistency of inchworm rotary motion. Firstly, the contact model of CSCRM can be simplified into a mass-spring-damping systems, as shown in Fig. 6(a) and (b), and the dynamic models of different contact status can be expressed as follows:

(1) Without contact: $x_{pzt} = S_{out}$

$$(M_1 + M_2) \ddot{x}_{pzt} = -K_1 x_{pzt} - C_1 \dot{x}_{pzt} \quad (11)$$

(2) In contact: $\Delta S_{out} = 0$

$$M_2 \ddot{S}_{out} = K_2 (x_{pzt} - S_{out}) + C_2 (\dot{x}_{pzt} - \dot{S}_{out}) + F_{con} \quad (12)$$

where $K_i = 1/C_i$ represents corresponding structural stiffness from equation (10), S_{out} can be accurately obtained by measuring the deformation of flexible hinges in the soft-contact head.

Besides, two-level contact stiffness acts as two serial buffers to effectively absorb contact vibration, as shown in Fig. 6(d). Then, assuming that there is an initial gap δ (measurable) between two surfaces before contact, as shown in Fig. 6(a), the relative velocity between contact head and output platform can be used to describe the contact and frictional status, and it can be expressed under desired contact status as follows:

$$\begin{cases} V_{cN} = V_i^{i+1} \cdot n = \delta^T \cdot n \\ V_{cT} = V_i^{i+1} \cdot t = \delta^T \cdot t \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where V_{cN} and V_{cT} are the normal velocity and tangential velocity, n and t represent the vector direction, respectively.

For desired contact status, it is necessary to strictly limit the frictional status as static friction (synchronous movement between two contact surfaces) to prevent slipping. Therefore, the contact force F_{con} (vertical pressure) and tangential relative velocity V_{rel} between two contact surfaces can be used to further ensure the frictional status [35]. Generally, Ambrosio coulomb friction model [36–38] is adopted to analyze the relationship between contact force and frictional status, which has the advantages of simple calculation and better continuity. Thus, F_{con} and V_{rel} can be used to express contact status:

(1) Without slipping between two contact surfaces: $V_{rel} = 0$

$$F_f = F_{act}, \text{ and } F_{act} < F_c \quad (14)$$

F_{act} is the driving force of the rotary input of CSCRM, and F_f is friction, and F_c is coulomb static friction.

(2) With slipping between two contact surfaces: $V_{rel} \neq 0$

$$\begin{cases} F_c = \mu c_d F_{con}, F_{act} \geq F_c \\ F_f = F_c \cdot \text{sgn}(V_{rel}) + k_v V_{rel} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where k_v is the viscous coefficient, μ is the surface friction coefficient, c_d is the velocity correction factor.

Fig. 6. Analytical diagram of contact and frictional status of CSCRM. (a) initial status, (b)~(c) dynamic model of contact and frictional status of CSCRM, (d) the absorption principle of vibration by flexible hinges.

Obviously, case (1) is the desired status of the designed piezoelectric rotary motor. Among them, F_{con} is the positive pressure generated by the CSCRM, as shown in Fig. 6(c). Combining equations (1), (10) and (12), F_{con} has the following relationship with the deformation Δx of the flexible hinges:

$$F_{con} = \frac{\Delta x}{C_{Ocon}^{Out}} = -K_2(x_{pzt} - S_{out}) - C_2(\dot{x}_{pzt} - \dot{S}_{out}) \quad (16)$$

Therefore, F_{con} can be calculated either through the established compliance model or by measuring the deformation Δx of the output flexible hinge in CSCRM. Finally, the established contact-friction model will be used to optimize the trajectory of driving signals to further eliminate frictional slipping and hence improve step consistency.

4. Optimization and simulation analysis

In order to improve the rotary performance of the designed piezoelectric rotary motor, the FEA simulation and structural parameters optimization have been carried out with the compliance model. Furthermore, the actuated signals and contact signals have also been optimized based on the contact-friction model to avoid frictional slipping and further suppress contact vibration through smooth driving signals.

4.1. Mechanical optimization of CSCRM

To improve the speed of rotary step displacement and mechanical stability of the CSCRM under high frequency, the structural parameters are optimized. Firstly, targeting the rotary step displacement S and mechanical natural frequency f of the CSCRM, the key dimensional parameters are optimized to improve dynamic properties based on the established compliance model. S_{rz} and S_y are mainly affected by the deformation of circular flexible hinges of CSCRM, when the CSCRM rotates around O_{R1} under actuation of F_{pzt2} , the compliance and displacement at O_{R1} can be expressed as follows:

$$C_{O_{R1}} = \left[(T_{R2}^{R1} C_{R2} T_{R2}^{R1})^{-1} + (T_{R3}^{R1} C_{R3} T_{R3}^{R1})^{-1} + C_{R1}^{-1} \right]^{-1} \quad (17)$$

To increase the speed and step length of rotary motion (S_{rz}), it is important to reduce the parasitic displacement (S_y) of CSCRM. So, the optimization function S_R for the conversion ratio of rotary motion is defined as follows:

Table 1
Optimized parameters of CSCRM.

Parameters	Results	Parameters	Results
l_1	4.0 mm	r_2	2.5 mm
t_1	0.5 mm	tr_2	0.6 mm
l_2	3.5 mm	S_{rz}	3.42 μm
t_2	0.6 mm	S_y	0.38 μm
r_1	2.5 mm	S_R	88.9 %
tr_1	0.8 mm	Frequency-1st	4130 Hz

$$S_y = F_{pzt2} \cdot C_{O_{R1}}(\Delta y, Fy) + M_{pzt2} \cdot C_{O_{R1}}(\Delta y, Mz) \quad (18)$$

$$S_{rz} = F_{pzt2} \cdot C_{O_{R1}}(\Delta \theta z, Fy) + M_{pzt2} \cdot C_{O_{R1}}(\Delta \theta z, Mz) \quad (19)$$

$$S_R = (S_{rz} - S_y) / S_{rz} \times 100\% \quad (20)$$

Besides, considering the requirement of height and mechanical machining of CSCRM, the height b and minimum thickness t of flexible hinge are determined as 12 mm and 0.5 mm, respectively. Specifically, the optimization objectives of CSCRM are: 1) $\min(S_R) > 85\%$ for ensuring enough rotary output and less parasitic displacement; and 2) $\min(f_1) > 4000$ Hz for a superior dynamic performance. It should be pointed out that S_{rz} can be expressed as either arc length displacement or corresponding rotary angle according to different requirements, which can be converted by mathematical relations. Then, the optimization range and initial value of other key parameters are determined by preliminary FEA results, and the optimization task is undertaken by genetic algorithm toolbox of MATLAB. Finally, the results of optimized parameters are listed in Table 1.

Fig. 7. Actuated trajectory optimization of the rotary motor. (a) the maximum rotary speed curves under different contact forces F_{con} , (b) the boundary conditions on frictional slipping for F_{con} and F_{act} , (c) optimized actuated trajectories of each PZT.

4.2. Actuated signals optimization of rotary motor

In order to eliminate the frictional slipping, the driving signals is optimized based on the boundary conditions from the established contact-friction model. Additionally, as the driving signals (in Fig. 4(f)) are too sharp and easy to result in contact vibration, a smoother and more stable actuated signal trajectory has also been developed.

According to the contact-friction model, the frictional slipping will not happen if the driving acceleration a_r is kept below the maximum acceleration of the ideal static friction status. Therefore, combining with the analysis in Fig. 6 and equation (14), the relationship of a_r between m_{load} and F_{con} can be expressed as follows:

$$a_r = \ddot{S}_{rz}(t) < \frac{\mu c_d F_{con}}{m + m_{load}} \tag{21}$$

here m and m_{load} represent the mass of the output platform and external load, respectively.

By combining the trapezoidal motion trajectory method with equations (14) and (21), the relationships between F_{con} , F_{act} , and a_r can be obtained, and the actuated trajectory is optimized for more stable motion. It can be seen that the permitted maximum rotary speed of CSCRM is restricted by F_{con} under same F_{act} , as shown in Fig. 7(a). Besides, the analysis of the relationships between F_{con} , F_{act} , and relative slipping is presented in Fig. 7(b). It can be seen that too large F_{act} and too small F_{con} will cause frictional slipping. Finally, with the deduced boundary condition in Fig. 7(a) and (b), the frictional slipping can be avoided by optimizing the driving signals in values, sequences and smooth shape, as shown in Fig. 7(c), which will be used in subsequent experiments and further verified.

4.3. FEA simulation and results analysis

To verify the mechanical performance after optimization, static analysis and modal analysis have been carried out by ANSYS Workbench. Among them, the relationship between output displacement and input forces of CSCRM is shown in Fig. 8(a) and (b), which indicates the output stiffness of CSCRM are 12.5 N/ μ m at contact direction, and 22.7 N/ μ m at rotary direction. Meanwhile, the mechanical modal of CSCRM is analyzed to reveal dynamic property, as shown in Fig. 8(c) and (d). The first and second natural frequencies are 4204.1 Hz and 5243.0 Hz, respectively, which shows that the high dynamic properties are similar to the results obtained by the optimization in Table 1 (1.8% deviation). In addition, the process of generating rotation of the designed rotary motor is analyzed, as shown in Fig. 8(e)~(h). According to the designed working flow (see Section II), it can be seen that the designed motor can rotate 0.27 mrad (the diameter of the simplified simulation model is 90 mm) with single CSCRM under input displacement 15 μ m, and also can generate 0.49 mrad by two CSCRM within one motion cycle. The simulation results show that the designed CSCRM can generate desired rotary output and will be compared with experimental results later.

Fig. 8. The FEA simulation results of CSCRM and the designed rotary motor. (a)~(b) the contact stiffness analysis of CSCRM, (c)~(d) the modal analysis of CSCRM, (g)~(h) simulation of the rotary generation process based on inchworm motion.

5. Experiment tests and discussions

In this section, the experimental prototype system has been established. A series of experiments have been conducted to verify the performance of designed mechanism and optimized driving signals in improving step consistency. First, the fundamental tests of the CSCRM have been carried out to verify the rotary performance under various contact force, gaining a desired contact force range with better performance in continuity and step consistency of output. Second, rotation tests with optimized driving signals under different frequencies have been performed, obtaining highest step consistency in the literature, i.e., 93% within 100 Hz. Third, motion consistency and stability under different loads have also been tested. Finally, the performance evaluation and analysis are carried out.

Fig. 9. Experimental validation system setup.

5.1. Experimental system setup

The whole experimental validation system is displayed in Fig. 9, the dual-driving CSCRM are mainly manufactured with AL7075-T6 through wire electrical discharge machining, and the rotary output platform (size is about \varnothing 100 mm) is composed of a high-precision bearing (RU42, EFANT) and alumina ceramic blocks for more stable and durable movement, this alumina ceramic block is bolted to the platform for easy installation and replacement. Among them, the single CSCRM is actuated by two piezoelectric ceramic actuators from Coremorrow Company (XMT-PS150/5 \times 5/20L, the piezoelectric coefficient is about: $d_{31}=-290$ pm/v, $d_{33}=+635$ pm/v and 180 layers of piezoelectric ceramic sheets), and voltage amplifier (E.03, XMT and E-503, PI). Besides, three linear capacitive displacement sensors (NS-DCS14, SYMC, resolution:20 nm) are used to detect the displacement of two soft-contact heads and the rotary angle, respectively. The motion system is controlled through dSPACE rapid prototyping simulating system (DS-1007, dSPACE) and all devices are placed on a vibration isolation platform (WN01AL, Winner optics).

Besides, to accurately measure the performance of the designed piezoelectric rotary motor, the experiments are carried out within the measuring range of sensor. The linear displacement is converted into the corresponding angle through mathematical relationships ($\theta=\arctan(L/r)$), which has high conversion accuracy in a small motion range.

5.2. The output performance tests under different contact status

5.2.1. Output performance tests of the CSCRM

To confirm the output characteristics of CSCRM and the step resolution of the rotary motor, several tests have been carried out. First, the stroke and resolution of contact and rotary motion of the CSCRM modules are tested respectively, as shown in Fig. 10(a)~(b). Among them, the contact stroke of CSCRM can reach about 15 μ m (PZT voltage is about 135 V), and maximum step size of CSCRM is 0.25 mrad at contact surface, while the resolution is less than 150 nm (the equivalent rotary angle is about 3.3 μ rad). The maximum step size is close to simulated results and the deviation is within 8% (0.27 mrad in Fig. 8(f)). Meanwhile, the contact process between the CSCRM and output rotary platform is tested to reveal the effectiveness of soft-contact head in introducing extra buffer after contact. When the initial gap δ is about 10 μ m, the displacement change of the soft-contact head under separation-contact-separation process is shown in

Fig. 10(c), which shows that the deformation of soft-contact head can more stably hold the position of output platform and act as a buffer to reduce vibration. Besides, the step signals are used to test the contact and rotary motions of the CSCRM. The results show the contact and rotary modules can work independently and successfully rotate the output platform with small contact vibration, as shown in Fig. 10(d). In summary, the above tests prove that the proposed CSCRM can generate high-precision step and rotate the output platform with small contact vibration.

Fig. 10. Performance tests of the CSCRM. (a) contact stroke test, (b) rotary stroke and resolution test, (c) contact process of the CSCRM with two-level contact stiffness, (d) rotation test of single step.

5.2.2. Influence of contact force on step consistency

In order to further analyze the influence of contact force on the step consistency of the inchworm rotary motor, the contact displacement of the soft-contact head is measured by the sensor, and the contact force is calculated indirectly based on the contact stiffness model and measured displacement. When the contact force is greater than 68.2 N (based on the conversion relationship $F = KX$ and measurement value), the rotary motor generates significant nonlinear contact vibration effects due to the overlarge contact force, as shown in Fig. 11(a). In addition, the contact force of 47.7 N will also result in contact vibrations of output platform under dynamic process, which directly cause output rollback, as shown in Fig. 11(b). Therefore, an overlarge contact force will cause the vibration and slipping of output platform. Meanwhile, combined with the contact-friction model (21), the minimum value of the contact force under the condition of non-slipping can be obtained. When the variation of contact force are in the range between 19.8 N~35.3 N, the rollback can be significantly reduced with less contact vibration but the step inconsistency is still obvious, as shown in Fig. 11(c).

Therefore, according to the experimental phenomena and the model results, the appropriate range of contact force is determined, which can reduce the vibration and slip problems of the partially rotary motor, and the experimental results are within the range of the model calculation. The drive signal trajectory will be further optimized based on this contact force range (20 N to 35 N) in the following experiments to improve step consistency.

5.3. Generation tests of rotary output motion

5.3.1. Rotary tests with different frequencies

In order to test the influence of different frequencies on the step consistency, rotary tests with 10 Hz, 20 Hz and 50 Hz have been carried out within desired contact force range mentioned above. First, according to the working flow of the dual-driving CSCRM (in Section II), the driving signals of PZTs without being optimized through the contact-friction model are used in the tests, as Fig. 12(a). The displacements of output platform under different frequencies within desired contact force range are tested, as shown in Fig. 12(b)~(d). From the results in Fig. 12(b), it can be seen that although the motion continuity can be improved and the rollback can be reduced by adopting a suitable contact range,

Fig. 11. Influence of different contact force on rotary output. (a)~(b) vibration, slipping and rollback caused by overlarge contact force, (c) step inconsistency caused by excessive difference of contact force between two CSCRM.

if the CSCRM on both sides cannot maintain similar contact and driving characteristics, the output consistency of the piezoelectric rotary motor is still difficult to improve. Besides, as the frequency increases, the contact vibration and frictional slipping gradually appears under square wave signals. Hence, simply controlling the contact force within an appropriate range is still not enough to ensure high step consistency of the piezoelectric rotary motor.

5.3.2. Rotary tests with optimized driving signals

To further enhance the step consistency of rotation under wide-range frequencies, the optimized driving signals based on contact-friction model are introduced and the rotary output characteristics under different frequencies are tested again, as shown in Fig. 13. Compared with the previous experiments in Fig. 12, optimized driving signals have greatly improve the smoothness of contact motion in Fig. 13(a). What's more, after adopting the desired contact force range and optimized driving signals, the nonlinear motion effects of inchworm rotary motor, such as rollback, contact vibration and frictional slipping, are effectively reduced compared with the previous experiments, as shown in Fig. 13(b)~(d).

Importantly, the step consistency of the piezoelectric rotary motor directly determines the stability and accuracy under large stroke after superposition. Therefore, we define step consistency S_{sc} to describe the ratio of equality between adjacent steps, which is calculated as follows:

$$S_{sc} = \frac{|(x_2 - x_1)| + |(x_3 - x_2)| + \dots + |(x_i - x_{i-1})|}{i \times d_{des}} \times 100\% \quad (22)$$

where x_i is the output displacement of step i , and d_{des} is the initial desired step size of the calculation.

According to the above calculation method, the step consistency ratios are higher than 93% within 100 Hz (highest in the current literature as shown in Table 2), showing the effectiveness of optimized driving signals in improving step

consistency. Moreover, the resolution, speed and frequency are $3.3 \mu\text{rad}$, 42.81 mrad/s and 100 Hz , which are also very competitive among current literature.

Fig. 12. Rotary tests under different frequencies with desired contact force range. (a) the driving signals without being optimized and properties of contact forces, (b)~(d) rotary angles of output platform under 10Hz/20Hz/50Hz.

Fig. 13. Rotary motion testing based on desired contact force range and optimized driving signals. (a) the driving signals and properties of contact forces, (b)~(e) rotary output properties under 10Hz/30Hz/50Hz/100Hz.

Fig. 14. The performance testing of rotary and contact motion under different loads. (a) rotary motion performance under different loads, (b) contact status testing under different loads.

Table 2

Comparison of the rotary motor with current typical works.

Ref.	Structural dimensions (mm)	Maximum driving voltage (V)	Size of PZT a×b×L (mm)	Step consistency	Resolution (μrad)	Loading capacity (kg)	Speed-to-diameter ratio	Frequency (Hz)	Torque (N·mm)
[18]	100×100×35	100	5×5×20	N/A	10	0.22	38.6	275	98.8
[22]	50×39×7	150	7×7×20	53%	4	0.5	48.3	20	50
[39]	φ20×25	100	4.5×3.5×20	80%	4.95	0.1	11.4	30	93.1
[40]	φ88×72	140	14×10×13.5	56%	10.3	0.25	13.6	150	73.5
[41]	100×10×25	150	N/A	73%	1.32	1.3	49.0	200	N/A
This work	φ100×30	150	5×5×20	93%	3.3	2	77.1	100	132.4

5.3.3. Output testing under different loads

On the other hand, the output characteristics of the designed rotary motor under different loads have also been tested. As the load increases, the variations of contact vibration of the CSCRM remain small, as shown in Fig. 14(b). Although the rotary stroke shows a trend of decrease due to insufficient contact force, the rotary output still maintains a good consistency and stability, as shown in Fig. 14(a).

5.4. Performance evaluation and discussion

Compared with the existing rotary motors with similar inchworm driving modes, the performance of the designed rotary motor is shown in Table 2. The developed rotary motor has following advantages: 1) The designed CSCRM and optimized dual-driving signals can effectively reduce contact vibration and frictional slipping, which ensures a large stable loading capacity of 2 kg and speed-to-diameter ratios of 77.1 (comparison of speeds after normalisation of output diameters); and 2) The optimized driving signals based on the contact-friction model can significantly improve the step consistency (beyond 93% within 100 Hz) ratio. Besides, the optimized driving signal increases the rise time and loses a few of the motion frequencies, which is a trade-off between two contradictory properties of vibration suppression and response speed. By comparison, it is more necessary to optimize the driving signal trajectory to improve motion stability and consistency.

6. Conclusions

The current inchworm piezoelectric rotary motors are severely suffered from contact vibration and frictional slipping, result in poor step consistency. In this article, a new inchworm piezoelectric rotary motor with optimized driving signals is presented and tested, obtaining the highest step consistency under different frequencies in the literature. In detail, the CSCRM contains contact module and rotary module, generating contact and rotation independently. Moreover, the contact module contains two-level contact stiffness, suppressing contact vibration and achieving more stable contact.

Furthermore, a contact-friction model is built to judge the boundary conditions of frictional slipping with consideration of acceleration under different frequencies. Based on this model, the driving signals of contact and actuation are optimized in value, sequence and shape, avoiding frictional slipping under different frequencies without readjusting initial gap. The experiments uniformly confirm that the developed rotary motor can achieve microradian resolution with $3.3 \mu\text{rad}$, speed of 42.81 mrad/s , and load-bearing capacity of 2 kg in a highly linear and stable manner. After adopting the proposed optimized driving signals based on contact-friction, the designed rotary motor attains the highest step consistency (93%) in the literature, greatly reducing contact vibration and frictional slipping.

It is also worth noting that the designed motor can continuously work across different frequencies without readjusting the initial gap, as the acceleration is limited by the optimized driving signals to avoid frictional slipping. In the future, we will establish closed-loop control methods to further improve anti-interference performance under different loads.

Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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